

THE MODERN PHARMACOLOGICAL AND THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES TO ANKYLOSING SPONDYLITIS: A REVIEW OF CURRENT GUIDELINES AND TREATMENT STRATEGIES

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Introduction

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic autoimmune disease primarily affecting the spine and lumbosacral joints, characterized by inflammation that can lead to significant disability. Associated with the human leukocyte antigen B27 (HLA-B27), AS affects 0.1-1.5% of the global population, with a notably higher prevalence in men, typically beginning before the age of 40. The disease has a profound impact on the quality of life, often leading to early disability among young adults. The chronicity of the disease, combined with its potential for severe functional impairment, highlights the importance of timely and effective treatment. The development of updated international guidelines, such as those from the Spondyloarthritis International and the European League Against Rheumatism (ASAS-EULAR) and the American College of Rheumatology (ACR/SAA), has provided new directions in managing AS. Despite significant advances, challenges persist, particularly regarding the long-term use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and the risk of side effects.

Materials and Methods

The research discussed in this thesis was based on an extensive review of the literature, focusing on the latest therapeutic strategies for treating AS, including pharmacological interventions and non-drug treatments. The study involves a systematic review of clinical trials, guidelines, and meta-analyses published from 2016 to 2022. Key sources included the most recent guidelines by ASAS-EULAR (2016) and ACR/SAA (2019), as well as clinical trials on new biologic therapies. Specific attention was given to the role of NSAIDs, disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs), and biologic therapies, including TNF- α inhibitors, IL-17 inhibitors, and Janus kinase inhibitors. Studies on safety profiles, efficacy, and long-term outcomes of these treatments were included, with a particular focus on adverse events associated with NSAIDs and the emerging role of IL-17 inhibitors like secukinumab and bimekizumab.

Results

The findings from the reviewed studies indicate significant advances in the pharmacological management of AS, particularly with the introduction of biologic therapies targeting specific pro-inflammatory cytokines. NSAIDs remain the first-line treatment for AS due to their effectiveness in controlling pain and inflammation. However, their long-term use is associated with serious side effects, including gastrointestinal ulcers, liver damage, and cardiovascular events, highlighting the need for careful management and risk assessment. Biologic treatments, particularly TNF- α inhibitors, have proven highly effective in reducing disease activity and improving patient quality of life. However, their use is not without challenges, such as secondary resistance in some patients.

Recent studies have demonstrated the efficacy of IL-17 inhibitors, including secukinumab, in slowing disease progression, especially in reducing radiological damage to the spine. The introduction of Janus kinase inhibitors like filgotinib and upadacitinib has further expanded treatment options, showing promise in NSAID-refractory patients. Bimekizumab, a selective dual inhibitor of IL-17A and IL-17F, showed rapid and sustained improvements in clinical outcomes, with over 60% of patients achieving significant disease control. However, concerns about safety remain, as the study reported a high number of adverse events.

While IL-17 inhibitors have demonstrated efficacy in controlling AS, questions remain about their role in comparison to TNF- α inhibitors. Some studies suggest that TNF- α inhibitors may not slow disease progression as effectively as IL-17 inhibitors, prompting ongoing research to compare these therapies head-to-head in large-scale trials. Additionally, the impact of IL-23 inhibitors on AS has been largely disappointing, with no substantial effect observed in clinical trials.

Conclusion

The treatment landscape for ankylosing spondylitis has evolved significantly with the introduction of targeted biologic therapies, especially those inhibiting IL-17. These treatments have shown considerable promise in reducing disease activity and preventing structural damage to the spine. However, challenges remain in terms of safety, long-term efficacy, and the management of side effects associated with long-term NSAID use. The need for personalized treatment approaches, considering the patient's specific disease phenotype and response to therapy, is clear. Future research should focus on further refining treatment algorithms, comparing the efficacy and safety profiles of different biologic agents, and exploring the potential of new therapeutic targets like IL-23. Additionally, guidelines should be updated to reflect emerging

evidence, particularly regarding the treatment of AS in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, to ensure that patients receive the most appropriate and effective care

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